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Prediction of Strength and Its Variation of Carbon Fiber Mat Reinforced Thermoplastics Using Monte-Carlo Method

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01 Background

The treatment of CFRP waste is becoming an urgent problem.

CFRP Market

The production of nonwoven mats for rCFs:

- ✓ Middle lengths: wet laid nonwoven production by **papermaking method**;
- ✓ Longer fibers: dry aligning methods like **carding, yarn spinning**.

- ✓ Many CFRPs have reached end-of-life, generating massive amounts of CFRP waste [1].
- ✓ Manufacturing process will produce up to 40% CFRP waste [2].

Mechanical recycling
Thermal recycling
Chemical recycling

[1] H. Sun, G. Guo, et al. Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf., 78, 10–17 (2015).

[2] F. Meng, J. McKechnie, SJ. Pickering. Compos Part A, 109, 207-20 (2018).

Carbon Fiber Mat Reinforced Thermoplastics (CMT)

- ✓ Show great potential for recycling and reusing waste carbon fibers (CFs) in high value-added products.
- ✓ The intermediate sheet with CFs and resin fibers can make CFRTP just by heat press without adding other materials.
- ✓ Good complex-shaped molding capabilities [3].

uncertainties

Predictions for the tensile properties

- ✓ During the producing process, uncertainties and nonuniform of mechanical properties are un-avoided.
- ✓ Fiber orientation is nonuniform in composites, so strength prediction based on **microscopic structure** is important.
- ✓ Limited by the number of experiments, experiment results will show some limitations. Thus, simulation with statistical considerations can clarify phenomena and significantly shorten product development time.

Monte-Carlo simulation

Stochasticity and statistical characteristics of the tensile properties

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2.1 Materials and specimen Preparation

CMT

carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics (CPT)

- CPT produced by CARMIX carbon fiber sheets (AWA Paper & Technological Company, Inc.), which is manufactured in the papermaking process by mixing carbon fibers with thermoplastic resin fibers using **wet papermaking technology**.
- Inexpensive prepreg for CFRP by making a prepreg in one process is achieved, which can **reduce the molding costs**.

non-woven carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (NW-CFTRP)

- NW-CFTRP is produced by carding processes (provided by Miraikasei Company, Inc.) with 50mm long CFs and PA6 fibers.
- Show large anisotropic properties.

2.1 Materials and Specimen Preparation

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2.2 Ash Test and Void Content Analysis

- The actual fiber volume fraction V_f and void content ratio V_v of each CPT panel were obtained by the ash test:

	CPT (A)			CPT (B)		
	MD	CD	Cross	MD	CD	Cross
V_f	28.90%	28.92%	29.12%	32.40%	32.45%	31.82%
V_r	70.74%	69.99%	70.10%	62.94%	63.35%	62.95%
V_v	0.36%	1.08%	0.78%	4.67%	4.20%	5.23%

	NW-CFRTP (A)		NW-CFRTP (B)		NW-CFRTP (C)	
	MD	CD	MD	CD	MD	CD
V_f	23.82%	24.27%	32.18%	32.06%	38.05%	37.69%
V_r	63.07%	63.11%	63.93%	64.41%	61.61%	61.94%
V_v	13.11%	12.62%	3.89%	3.53%	0.34%	0.37%

- Void content analysis

ImageJ →

python →

2.3 Tensile Test

- Tensile properties were measured by axial tensile test according to JIS K 7073 with a universal testing machine (AUTOGRAPH AGS-X plus 100KN, Shimadzu Co., Ltd.).
- With higher CF Vf, both tensile modulus and tensile strength are improved due to the fact that there are more CFs contributing to sustaining the loading.

2.4 Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

- DIC tracks the movement of the naturally occurring or applied surface pattern during experiments.

2.5 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

- Fiber slippage can be observed by SEM after breakage.
- Furthermore, fiber-fiber contact points can be observed in amplified figures.

CMT after breakage observed by SEM

2.6 X-ray micro-CT scanning

inspeXio SMX-100CT X-ray scanning system (Shimadzu Co., Ltd.)	
tubular voltage	60 kV
tubular current	90 μ A
distance	10 mm

Schematic of the X-ray scanning process and scanned volume.

CPT

NW-CFRTP

Stereogram (a) and floor plan (b) of X-Ray scanning; orientation distributions of in-plane (c) and out-of-plane (d) angles.

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3.1 Evaluation of the fiber orientation distribution (FOD)

- The TRI/3D-FBR-DT software (RATOC System Engineering, Co., Ltd., Japan) was employed to obtain FOD.
- Evaluation of FODs of in-plane angles.

Fiber orientation distributions of in-plane angles.

- Amplitude version of Gaussian peak function:

$$y = y_0 + Ae^{-\frac{(x-x_c)^2}{2w^2}}$$

y_0 is the offset; x_c is the center; w is the width; A is the amplitude.

	CPT			NW-CF RTP	
	MD	CD	Cross	MD	CD
y_0	0.0329	0.0496	0.0227	0.0357	0.0413
x_c	0.8871	86.9588	88.6048	-0.2376	89.9665
w	29.6297	16.7366	25.1914	11.9794	10.6401
A	0.0537	0.0256	0.0936	0.0792	0.0777
FWHM	69.7727	39.4117	59.3211	28.2094	25.0555
Area	3.9887	1.0741	5.9078	2.3774	2.0726

3.1 Evaluation of the fiber orientation distribution (FOD)

- Evaluation of FODs of out-of-plane angles.

	CPT			NW-CFRTP	
	MD	CD	Cross	MD	CD
$90^\circ \pm 1^\circ$	5.3%	5.63%	5.74%	15.74%	15.17%
$90^\circ \pm 3^\circ$	21.83%	22.99%	19.71%	33.72%	34.74%
$90^\circ \pm 5^\circ$	25.58%	26.61%	24.01%	39.90%	40.46%
$90^\circ \pm 10^\circ$	31.02%	32.22%	32.39%	46.00%	46.76%

Fiber orientation distributions of out-of-plane angles.

3.2 Model framework

- As for the fiber network model, all fibers were geometrically identical, and regarded as the smallest reinforcing units considered in this study.
- CFs were distributed based on randomly generated coordinates and specific FOD fitted by X-Ray scanning results.

Schematic of the 3D analytical model and contact points between fibers

FOD created by Monte-Carlo simulation and tested by X-Ray scanning

3.3 Characteristics of contact points

- Interactions between CF fibers were regarded as the non-bonded type, consisting of adhesion and friction force [4].

Adhesion and friction forces can be non-dimensionalized using fiber modulus E_f and diameter d :

$$\Psi_{Adh} = F_{Adh}/E_f d^2, \quad \Psi_{Fric} = F_{Fric}/E_f d^2$$

$$\Psi_{Adh}(\alpha) = \hat{\Psi}_{Adh}/\sin\alpha, \quad \Psi_{Fric}(\alpha) = \hat{\Psi}_{Fric}/(\sin\alpha)^{1/2}$$

- Parameters used in the 3D fiber network model.

		Value	Unit	Source
geometric parameters				
fiber length	L_f	6	mm	numerical
fiber diameter	d_f	7	μm	numerical
coordinates of endpoints of fibers	(x, y, z)	—	mm	generated
distribution of in-plane and out-of-plane angles	$\mu_{in}, \sigma_{in}, \mu_{out}, \sigma_{out}$	—	—	fitted
elastic constants				
tensile modulus of fibers	E_f	230	GPa	numerical
tensile modulus of PA6	E_m	3.2	GPa	numerical
characteristics of contacts				
contact stiffness penalty	K_p	$100E_f d_f$	N/mm	ref. [11]
frictional model parameter	μ	0.21	—	assumed

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4.1 Prediction of tensile moduli

- The netting analysis treats the laminate as a net with the ignorance of the fiber diameter and considers the loading of fiber ends, which is proposed by Cox [5].

Elastic moduli along the longitudinal (E_L) direction can be calculated:

$$E_L = E_f V_f (c_{11} - c_{22}^2 / c_{12}) + E_m (1 - V_f)$$

where,

$$c_{11} = \int_0^\pi \cos^4 \phi f(\phi) \phi, \quad c_{22} = \int_0^\pi \sin^4 \phi f(\phi) \phi,$$

$$c_{12} = \int_0^\pi \cos^2 \sin^2 \phi f(\phi) \phi$$

$$\int_0^\pi f(\phi) d\phi = 1.$$

Predicted and experimental tensile modulus.

Predicted tensile modulus for CPT-Cross

4.1 Prediction of tensile moduli

- Distribution of local tensile modulus

(a) Local predicted tensile modulus for CPT(A)-MD

(b) Local predicted tensile modulus for CPT(A)-CD

4.2 Prediction of tensile strength

- Algorithm

The input is the force applied to the specimen, which is increased during the simulation. Then, *the frictional force at contact points* can be calculated.

If applied force is *larger* than frictional force at the point, this point is regarded as a *slipping one*. When several slipping contacts can be linked to form a failure path, applied force will be output. If not, the applied force will increase continuously until a failure path is created.

Flow chart of tensile strength prediction

04 Results and Discussion

4.2 Prediction of tensile strength

- Progress of sliding contact points can be predicted till failure path is generated based on *Dijkstra's algorithm* [6] when calculating local tensile strength.

(a) Percentage of sliding contacts during tensile tests

(b) Development of contact points during tensile tests

(c) Stress distribution

(d) Fracture surface

Schematic of strength prediction: (a) Sliding contact points and fracture path; (b) Stress distribution and failure units; (c) Fracture surface

[6] Dijkstra EW. Numer. Math., 1, pp. 269-271 (1959).

4.2 Prediction of tensile strength

- Prediction results for CPT: Prediction results were consistent with the experimental results. However, as for CPT-CD, prediction methods tend to overestimate tensile strengths, due to prediction methods without strain hardening.

Prediction and experimental results of stress-strain curves (a-c) and tensile strengths (d).

4.3 Statistical characteristics

- Based on Monte-Carlo simulation, a series of repeated random simulations are carried out to obtain numerical results.
- As simulation number increases, standard deviation of predicted tensile modulus and strengths will converge to a stable value.

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Conclusion

- A 3D analytical model was achieved with non-bonded fiber-interaction types based on simulated FOD results.
- Satisfactory prediction results of tensile moduli and strengths were obtained.
- The scatter and stable standard deviation can be predicted, making it possible for CMT to be applied in recycling and industries.

Future Work

- The situation of inconsistent length of carbon fibers and bending carbon fibers can be considered so that the model can be used to other carbon fiber mat materials.
- Linear elastic characteristics with small strains during tensile were considered, without predicting strain hardening. Further comprehensive and insightful theoretical studies about forces in contacts will be carried out in the future in order to obtain a better understanding of the simulation of CMTs.

Thank you for your kind attention!

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